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**SOCIO-SPATIAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF THESSALONIKA WITHIN-THE
-WALLS (1890-1988)**

PART A

T E X T

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Abstract

Thessalonika -a city in Northern Greece established in the late fourth century B.C.- acquired its initial plan during the hellenistic period; its lay-out from then up to 1891 was a product of a natural, organic process of the city's growth.

Up to 1923 the city was inhabited by three major ethnical groupings, the Greeks (native population), the Turks (the rulers) and the Jews (controlling the city's market). This population was distributed in different quarters of the city that became all the more segregated up to the beginning of this century. Along this period, the city's lay-out was differentiated in its parts, reflecting differences in its social composition.

The first alteration of its physical fabric happened in 1890 when a fire destroyed the main Jewish quarters. A new, "modern" plan was designed for the burnt area and its implementation started in 1891.

A second fire in 1917 destroyed almost all the inner-city area and rendered the population homeless. The new plan prepared in the same year was designed according to the neoclassical principles and the population was not rehoused according to their previous landholdings, but to the estimated value of their properties before the fire. Historical evidence reveals the radical change of population from groupings along ethnic lines to an arrangement according to zoning principles and income status.

The transformation of the physical fabric will be examined to see to what extent there are similarities or differences between the spatial structure of the city in different periods in time and how much do they relate to their corresponding socioeconomic structure.

The hypothesis of the study is first that the pre-1917 city and more precisely the 1890 city should reflect in the articulation of its spatial system the social composition of the population as well as their socioeconomic activities and the different way they produced their residential areas; second, the 1891 Plan alters slightly the city's spatial structure, since it is produced by the very same social system; third, the 1917 Neoclassical Plan alters drastically the same structure, following and to some extent challenging the social transformation of the city developing it to the city-core of a much broader arrangement; it is the first application of zoning system; fourth, the Modern Plan alters considerably the spatial properties of the Neoclassical Plan. The multiplied links with the carrier reduce the coherence and diversity of the city, transforming it even deeply to a subsystem of the whole metropolitan area; there had also been a comprehensive application of zoning principles; fifth, the up-to-date city within-the-walls continues to perform increased relations with the "extra-muros" city, tending to be organised in a rather multi-focal pattern, decentralising its main central-area functions; generative elements of previous typologies and mix of land-uses gain significance in order zoning principles to retreat and the city within-the-walls to be transformed to a coherent and diversified urban space.

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1. General problem statement

1.2. Utopian Planning

1.3 Morphological Descriptions

**1.4. Sociological Theories of the
City**

1.5. Problem Definition

1.1. General problem statement

Organic/unplanned cities have grown through accumulation processes, piecemeal development and lack of superordinate rules, involving history in a rather sedimentary process.

Semi-lattice is the outcome of two or more mutually superimposed subsystems belonging to the same system. A tree in mathematical terms is a system that one or more subsystems are included by another subsystem or that one or more subsystems have no common elements between themselves. In terms of urban space it implies "mono-functional" environments where land-uses are distributed according to a zoning arrangement.

Growth is artificial when involving a major break to the pre-existing rules of a spatial structure: a neoclassical plan applied on an organically grown city can be considered as an artificial growth, because neoclassical cities are superimposed on a preexisting structure, thus disrupting the links with the immediate past.

The above polar oppositions (organic/neoclassical, unplanned/planned, natural/artificial, semi-lattice/tree) need, beyond their precise definition, a clarification of the underlying reasons for their existence and development.

Trade developed in organic, unplanned cities in a semi-lattice pattern coexisting with other uses (i.e. housing). When replaced by marketing, the latter provided the urban physical space with an artificial growth, the land-uses developing in a tree-like pattern (zoning). Besides, with the advancement of technology, accessibility lost its initial importance shifting

from competition on physical proximity to competition on accessibility to information via intangible channels of communication.

Moreover, history provides us with evidence that oppressed and low-income communities have been marginalised in the most isolated parts of their cities and provided with the lowest accessibility potential to their city-centre. Besides, the spatial patterns of their residential areas, when imposed by another ruling class, obey gridiron or/and zoning principles.

Urban environments that grew on ethnical lines have been close to organic, unplanned, natural patterns distributing their land-uses in a semi-lattice process. When their physical space was organised rationally by another ruling group, the physical pattern shifted to a planned urban space on neoclassical or modern principles and semi-lattice was replaced by a "tree-like" arrangement.

There seems to be a fundamental relationship between accessibility patterns or integration of space and social division, or integration of space and the division of labour.

Environments acquire their form and order as a result of a social process. Through its ordering of space, the man-made physical world constitutes (not merely represents) a form of order in itself: one which is created for social purposes, whether by design or accumulatively and through which society is both constrained and recognisable. Hence, the rules of spatial arrangements have to be sought in society itself.

According to Durkheim, societies deploy themselves in space through the function of different forms of social solidarity or cohesion; "organic" solidarities -based on interdependence through differences, such as those resulting from the division of labour- and "mechanical" solidarities -based on integration through similarities of belief and group structure- affect

spatial and "transpatial" systems and their dynamics and it is them to be explored if a spatial order is to be revealed.

1.2. Utopian Planning

"Utopia" etymologically means lack of space or even refusal of space (Utopia=non "topos", non place). Here it is conceptualised as the process radically replacing a pre-existing spatial structure or, in other words, as a set of (a-spatial) planning principles concerned with setting a new order in space, different from a pre-existing one.

Social order at a given period in time means agreement between differential solidarities. Lack of agreement leads to social-and spatial-disorder or the appearance of a new social order set by the most powerful. Put it another way, every radical transformation of urban space is achieved through the implementation of a Utopian plan performing the already transformed social order, or a desired one by those who have the power to impose it.

Superimposed order on societies led always to a spatial order characterised by modular or/and orthogonal gridiron plans, clusters and mononuclear (concentric) arrangements, while democratic societies developed always bi-or-multi-focal spatial orders: neoclassical plans have been superimposed on their societies by the developing rich and powerful middle-class (merchants etc) that replaced monarchy with preliminary democratic processes setting a new spatial arrangement (fig.1). Syntactically, they reflect the loosened descriptive physical control of the ruling class on the spatial order of the community.

Era	Social Order	Urban Pattern
Early Antiquity	monarchy	geomorphic
Mature "	democracy	bi-focal concentric
Hellenistic	"	bi-focal,orthogonal linear
Roman	monarchy	modular gridiron, clusters
Medieval	"	concentric
Renaissance	"	clusters
Mannerism	"	modular gridiron, clusters
Baroque	"	clusters
Colonialism	"	modular gridiron, clusters
Mercantilism	democracy	bi-focal orthogonal linear

Neoclassic.	early capit.	gridiron orthogonal
Social Reform.	" "	clusters
Modernism	capitalism	modular gridiron
Futurism	" "	" "

Fig. 1. Social and corresponding spatial order in European history.

Moreover, Utopian planning in early and mature Modern periods imposed rigid plans with asymmetric and non-distributed syntaxes using the "no-neighbours" principle and setting strong descriptive physical control on the large aggregate: from the factory communities of Robert Owen and the phalansteries of Fourier (reformism), to the garden cities of Howard and the technological romances of Le Corbusier (early and mature modernism), the fundamental idea is the design of peaceful industrial production (social order) by the redesign of the spatial form of communities using a new urban genotype (spatial order): space has to be arranged in a way such as to organise society not in p-models (phenotypes) in which symmetric and distributed relations predominate, but in g-models (genotypes).

Howard i.e. proposed the desegregation of cities and their internal fragmentation into non-interchangeable zones, ordered by a strong exogenous model. In all cases the community was ideally small and the limited encounters were non random and strongly controlled.

But a democratically deployed in space society needs to be large, not small.

with dense nat sparse local encounter rates, non corresponding rather than corresponding social labels, locally and globally open, distributed and non-hierarchical.

1.3. Morphological descriptions

C.Sitte argued that it is not worthwhile dealing with big urban structures since they do not involve any aesthetic value perceivable by human beings (Sitte 1986). Rossi's criticism on Sitte's work is that the city is not a mere succession of perceptive images more or less intelligible, but more importantly, the whole has more importance than the parts and that one has to conceive the urban topography as a whole (Rossi, 1982).

Conzen's contribution in the field remains a method of classification of the spatially static characteristics of the urban space at a given period in time; he has no mechanism to compare successive or different in-time periods, the town plan remaining a descriptive analysis of the city's growth.

According to Chr. Alexander, a naturally grown city has the organisation of a "semi-lattice" and modern design has produced urban spaces on the principle of a "tree". He, too, is more concerned with providing tools for intervention than for analysis.

M. Tafuri describes a supra-historical process and involves every criticism in ideology; he tells us, however, a little about the fundamental process of Urban design as a medium and as a language, and hence, his work is rather explanatory than instrumental.

A.Rossi reintroduces the elements of history and typology: history becomes analogous to a skeleton serving as a measure of time and

bearing the imprint of the actions that take place in the city; the skeleton is a collective artifact, a record of events and a record of time. Typology becomes the "apparatus" of time's measurement. Monuments are primary elements in the city, persistent and characteristic urban artifacts distinguished from housing -the other primary element of the city- by their nature as a place of symbolic function, and thus a function related to time, as opposed to a place of conventional function, which is only related to use. They are dialectically related to the city's growth, with their double attribute of permanence and primary element of the urban realm; when primary elements are defined as retarding or accelerating the process of urbanisation, they are considered to be correspondingly "pathological" or "propelling". In the second case they serve to bring the past into the present ("locus solus").

With the introduction of memory into the object, type becomes an analytical and experimental structure which can be used to operate on the skeleton of history; it becomes an apparatus, an instrument for analysis and measure. Furthermore, typology which previously consisted only of the classification of the known, now can serve as a catalyst for invention.

Nevertheless, Rossi's main contribution is the clarification of a series of useful concepts and not an instrumental tool for analysis and comparisons.

Kriers call for the development of recognisable open-space types where the typology is devised not only from contemporary vernacular practice and historic tradition, but also from a deep concern for the reformation of the urban society along Marxist lines. The adoption of the scale of the individual, the end of zoning system and instead of it the encouragement of the autonomous quarters (cities within the city), the re-foundation of Urban design principles on the intelligence of history are the main points

of their argument.

In general, the work of New Rationalists can be revealed through what Vidler calls "the third typology". There the city constitutes a typology by itself and for itself. But in almost all post modernists' work there is an obvious lack of instrumental tools for urban spatial analysis.

Space Syntax theory provides the analytical tools for the Urban space relating design processes to knowledge, or otherwise, social to spatial order. Social order can always be explored through the historical records while spatial order through a language developed to describe and then analyze the deep structure of the urban space (alpha syntactic analysis of settlements). Hence, urban-space analysis becomes a dense language relating design elements to a dictionary, seeking thus, for structure below the visible, focusing on deep genotypical structure (genotypes) and not phenotypical ones (phenotypes).

For this school of thought, type is an identifiable structure, an abstract principle clarified through the morphological analysis, and thus, it carries knowledge.

If typology can be identified as an accumulated knowledge of urban types and morphology as an instrumental tool for the spatial analysis of urban complexes, and if we accept that space overcomes knowledge with all its particularities in any case, then morphology overcomes typology and becomes a mode of communicating between different typologies. Therefore, morphology and not typology reveals the kind of spatial order and decides if something works or not.

Space Syntax describes space in such a way as to make its social origins and consequences a part of that description. In that sense, the

social structure sheds light on the physical structure.

Territoriality theory suggests that if space has any importance at all in the ordering of social relations, it can only be by virtue of a correspondence between segments of space and segments of society. Social and spatial order can only be described and analyzed in terms of a "fit" between bounded social groups and the tangible physical zones which contain them. But territoriality theory implies clear boundaries between social groupings and strong hierarchies reflected in space (correspondence model).

In contrast, the non-correspondence model involves as a defining feature of an acting out in space and time of "transpatial" relations in a non-correspondence system cross-cutting local networks and generating and affirming enduring ties among people who normally live in entirely different places and who rarely encounter each other in daily life (Hanson and Hillier, 1987).

In the "Man -Environment Paradigm and his Paradoxes" the central idea is that social sciences do not any more conceive the urban physical space as a far background of urban intervention, but as a form of social behaviour. (Hillier and Leaman, 1973).

In every society where there are differences in subculture, class, gender or generational roles, they are realised in different principles of social cohesion within and between these groups and it is them that mould space and give it its material form (Hillier et al., 1987).

Therefore, the analytical tools have to relate the local organisation to the global structure without losing either its local identity or its global relatedness.

Space syntax conceives spatial order as a continually evolving structure assimilating the permanent as well as the casual elements. This latter

distinction is the distinction between genotypes and phenotypes (g-and-p models), the genotype considered as the generative rule governing a variety of concrete arrangements (Hillier and Hanson, 1984).

There can be defined two fundamental spatial orders: the syntactic one (the spatial organisation in terms of its physical arrangement) and the land-use order (the outcome of socio-economic and planning processes). The interrelationships between them and more importantly, between them and their corresponding social order seem to be the key-issues to investigate in order to analyze and interpret a socio-spatial arrangement.

1.4. Sociological theories of the city

The review of literature in this section aims at clarifying instrumental tools for social analysis and pinpointing the major social transformations of cities from the "proto"-industrial era and onwards.

The studies of urbanisation correlate economic development and social changes with the organisation of space (human ecology): the city is the ecological unity of a population set within a certain spatial context (Park, Hawley). According to Mckenzie the city is interpreted as a result of mere generalised ecological processes (concentration, centralisation, transportation networks, diversification, invasion and succession); nevertheless, these models perform a closed interpretative system where the social phenomena are interpreted again by social phenomena and not the reasons they produce them.

The criticism addressed to human ecology (Alihan, Firey, Kolb, Sojberg)

derives its opposition from the interpretation of the relation space/society, considered again in terms of a linear correlation with an interpretative character.

For phenomenologists, the core relation is that of the directly experienced other, the analysis of "we-relationships" (Schutz, Weber). They deal with action as meaning rather than praxis, not recognising the centrality of power in social life, thus not offering much upon problems of institutional transformation and history (Giddens 1978).

For Giddens institutionalised features of social systems have structured properties in the sense that relationships are stabilised across time and space. The basic domain of the study of social sciences is "social practices ordered across space and time" (Giddens 1984).

The problem of "order" is to explicate how the limitations of individual presence are transcended by the "stretching" of social relations. Interaction in circumstances of co-presence is one basic component of the "bracketing" of time-space that is both condition and outcome of human social association, and implies social integration, the last conceptualised as "systemness in circumstances of co-presence" (Giddens 1984).

Social interaction can be examined in relation to the different locales through which the daily activities of individuals are coordinated -locales not just as places-, but settings of interaction used chronically by social actors.

Within this context, there can be defined two major kinds of spatial logic of society, the correspondence and non-correspondence models. "It is to the conditions under which these two kinds arise and the dynamics of such systems as they grow, that we need to look, in order to reveal the social logic of space" (Hillier and Hanson 1987).

The correspondence model, in order to reproduce itself as a strong and stable statistical pattern, tends to reinforce the local group, but also keep it exclusive; it also tends to grow strong and stable emphasising physical separation of spatial groups and closed boundaries.

In contrast, a system works on non-correspondences when locally emphasises openness, continuity of space, lack of local enclosure and permeability of those boundaries which do exist. It works more probabilistically than deterministically, tolerating much more local disorder and yet being reproducible.

Zoning system -the most rigid form of spatial order analogous to the correspondence model of social order- appeared when planned cities replaced organically grown ones. It led to "mono-functional" urban space coming out of a rationalisation process, where the allocation of land-uses served some distinct social interests. From the "proto"-industrial era and onwards it contributed to the desegregation of the formatted social classes, the powerless low-income ones forced to live in the periphery of the cities (highly hierarchical "dormitory" zones). In contrast, the rich still retained the control of the city-centre by residing and working there.

The growth of C.B.D. produced its transitional zone, mostly hit by the urban blight, due to the fact that landowners in these areas waited for higher yields of their landholding through the alteration of the allowed land-uses. The blight favoured the deprivation of these inner-city areas that attracted low-income people and migrants transformed to industrial workers. The rich were no more residing there, but grace to the multiplied transportation networks, they occupied the clean peripheries. Thus, the zoning system applied in the pre-and-proto-industrial periods was reversed in the industrial one, but in both cases the city had been controlled by

the rich that retained high accessibility to the city-centre.

Zoning system has also been used in order to marginalise minorities with different ethnic -and hence, cultural- identities. Oppressed communities are frequently excluded in areas with concrete boundaries, strictly defined land-uses and low accessibility potential to the city-centre.

Apart from the residential areas, zoning has been involved during the industrial era in the ordering of central-area functions where the most accessible parts ("C.B.D.-core") have been occupied by the richest companies and the flourishing tertiary sector.

1.5. Problem definition

In Thessalonika, the passage from the hellenistic city to the Byzantine one is characterised by the establishment of feudalism, the urban space confined within the walls for security purposes as well as the condensation of the urban development that produced the "organic" city.

The most radical change in the city's social structure happened in the beginning of this century and this is due to the political alterations -in 1923 the region of Macedonia becomes Greek-, the economic recession and the exchange of populations between Greece and Turkey.

In 1917 a big fire destroyed almost all the inner-city area. The Greek government saw the event as a major challenge and exercised full control on the planning processes that followed.

The Turks left the city in 1923 according to the programme of populations' exchange between Turkey and Greece. Hence, we may assume that the city's socioeconomic structure up to 1923 had largely

remained stable. While the Turks were forced out, a massive wave of Greek refugees from western Turkey came to settle in the city, making the Greek community an overwhelming majority. This same infusion of new population caused the city to expand outside its walls and to occupy an area about four times its original size.

These major shifts in the population composition and distribution produced successive changes in the physical structure of the city: a neoclassical plan replaced the pre-existing organic one, to be replaced itself during the modern and post-modern periods by the corresponding modern and post modern plans.

According to the historical evidence, the city's social structure has changed drastically over time and this has to have caused essential changes in the city's spatial structure.

The study examines the city's social and spatial structures as well as their interrelationships and transformations in four periods in time: a) the pre-1890 Thessalonika, when the city still retained its old traditional social organisation of the three ethnic groups and its spatial lay-out remained largely unaffected, a1) the period between 1891 and 1917 when, although the social configuration remains almost stable, the spatial articulation is altered due to the plan of 1891 after the fire of 1890; b) the 1920 period when the 1917 plan after the big fire of 1917 is legitimated and the social structure remains largely stable; c) the modern era of the mid 1970s where there is a remarkable homogenisation of population and a comprehensive application of the modern city-planning and d) the late 1980s when the population homogenisation is stabilised and modern city-planning is largely disputed.

The (a) and (a1) periods are examined together for their strong interlinks. The examination and comparison between these four stages is

based on the understanding of the fundamental differences or/and similarities between them in terms of their socio-spatial structure (differential solidarities producing different city-plan typologies).

The organic plan of the city was replaced by a neoclassical one and this transformation might have improved accessibility to market areas, the Greek administration and developing tertiary sector, the public buildings and open public spaces contributing to the restoration of the community's identity. The first applications of the zoning system might have affected the distribution of the emerging new classes in the city.

When the neoclassical plan was modified by the modern one, a much more comprehensive application of zoning principles could be expected, the tertiary sector gaining all the more better accessibility values; moreover, accessibility in residential areas may have been significantly differentiated according to income.

During the post-modern era, when accessibility from physical proximity shifted to control of intangible channels of communication, zoning system is expected to retreat from the city-centre and the mix of residential with central-area functions to be encouraged. The accessibility potential of the marginalised low-income communities with respect to the city-centre and public facilities is expected to be found increased.

The study tests the above hypothesis and attempts to investigate to what extent the general statements about socio-spatial transformations of the cities in their transition from the pre-to the industrial era and up to post-modern ages have any (and the kind of) relation with the socio-spatial transformations that Thessalonika underwent.

CHAPTER II: METHODS

2.1. The method of Spatial Analysis

2.1. The method of spatial analysis

The analytic method for the rigorous numerical study of settlements used in this work is the Space Syntax analysis developed at the Unit of Architectural studies, University College London (Hillier, Hanson). This method attempts to detect and reveal the objective global and local properties of urban space.

The basic concepts are "symmetry-asymmetry" and "distributedness-non-distributedness". The relation of a space (a) to a space (b) is symmetric if the relation of (a) to (b) is the same as the relation of (b) to (a); if this is not the case, then the relation is asymmetric and it always involves some notion of depth, since we must pass through some third space to go from one space to the other.

A relation between two spaces (a) and (b) is distributed if there are more than one non-intersecting routes from (a) to (b) and non-distributed if there is only one. In a non-distributed system there are never more than one routes from one point to any other, whereas in a distributed system routes always form rings.

Having as a basis these measures, we can measure the degree to which any configuration of space is, convexly or axially, distributed or non-distributed, symmetric or asymmetric in its whole and in its parts. The more descriptions are symmetric (with respect to buildings or the whole carrier of a settlement, that is X and Y) then the more there will be a tendency to the integration of social categories (such as the categories of inhabitant and stranger or groups of people of different ethnicities), while conversely the more they are asymmetric then the more there will be a tendency to the segregation of social categories; while the more descriptions are distributed (again with respect to X and Y) then the more

there will be a tendency toward the diffusion of spatial control, while non-distributedness will indicate a tendency toward a unitary, superordinate control.

The structure of the urban public space can be analyzed looking rigorously at space first in terms of enclosure -that is how the articulation of the facades of buildings creates and shapes the public realm in terms of spaces which vary from one another in terms of their two-dimensional organisation. The syntactic equivalent for enclosure is convexity. A convex space is one in which any two points in the segment can be joined by a straight line which does not go outside the boundary of the space.

The advantage of convexity compared to enclosure is that it is fully objective -that is any number of people performing the break-up should arrive at the same convex map. Furthermore, convexity differs from enclosure in that it does not locate observer in the system; it can be measured by connectivity and it helps to reveal the local properties of space.

The main global property of space is what it could be perceived as the "sequencing of spaces" -lines of "sight and unimpeded access" through public space turning the building facades to long views through the urban space. The syntactic equivalent for this concept is axiality -the longest possible one-dimensional lines of both sight and unimpeded access that can be drawn between the facades of buildings formulated along the streets and other public spaces. Hence, axiality refers to the global organisation of the system and therefore, its organisation with respect to movement into and through the system; it is objective for the same reasons with convexity.

Axiality analyses the maximum extension of a unified space projected through the system thus providing the global properties of the urban

space, instead of convexity that deals with the local properties of convex break-up. Besides, the property of axiality has been found empirically to be related with use and movement patterns.

The most important variables related to convexity and axiality are:

a) grid axiality: $GA = \frac{L}{\sqrt{IX^2} + 2}$ where I: number of islands

L L: " " lines

when $GA=1$, perfect orthogonal grid.

Values of 0.25 and above indicate a relatively gridiron system and of 0.15 and below an axially more broken-up system. L corresponds to the distributed lines of the system. Grid axiality helps to test to what extent a given urban structure is a deformed grid or not.

b) Another way to measure the axial deformity is to measure the mean number of links, or connections between axial lines, that is the line-link ratio (LLR). This should be compared with a tree, which always has a line-link ratio of 1.00 (the ratio for housing estates is below 1.5, small towns or villages 1.5 or 1.6, "organic" towns 1.8 to 2.1, the neoclassical plans to or above 3.1, and the modern plans even higher values),

c) Depth (D): The depth of an axial line, with respect to another one in the same system, is the least number of axial lines or "steps" which are necessary to pass in order to go from one line to the other. The concept of depth can also be used to look at the relation between the city and its surroundings, in order to reveal striking properties of the street system. This can be represented by a series of maps which start at the city boundaries and count the numbers of turnings needed to go from the outside world to the city's heart, along all possible routes. Empirically, the shallower the depth of a point (a) from another (b), the less turnings and, hence, the easier to go from (a) to (b). The Mean Depth of a line (MD) is the average of all the depth values of this line calculated with respect to

each of the other lines in the system.

The depth of the system itself as related to its parts, is calculated by the mean depth of every space, and is a measure of how distant the parts of the system are from each other in terms of axial steps.

The Relative Asymmetry (RA) of a line is a number indicating how deep the system appears from this line, compared to how deep it could possibly have been if all its lines were arranged in a uni-linear sequence away from the original space. The formula for RA is $RA=2(MD-1)/(k-2)$, where (k) is the number of axial lines in the system. The values of RA vary between 0.00 and 1.00, with low values indicating that the system appears relatively shallow from this line, or that this line tends to bring the whole system closer, or to integrate it, whereas high values indicate that the line is relatively remote and segregated from the whole system, which appears very deep from it. Low RA values mean high integrating values and the opposite.

The Mean Relative Asymmetry (MRRRA) is the average RA of all lines of the system, and indicates the degree to which the whole system is equivalently related to its parts, how its parts are integrated or segregated from the whole; the formula is: Mean Relative RA (MRRRA)=MRA/Dk, where (Dk) is the MRA of a settlement of the same number of lines (k), but within which the distribution of lines has as follows: n lines are at the mean depth level, n/2 at the levels immediately below and above that, n/4 at two levels below and above, and so on, until there is 1 line at the shallowest points. Since the MRRRA gives the degree to which the whole system relates within itself, that is, it reflects the degree to which its parts are integrated or segregated from each other, it refers to global spatial relations, i.e. relations affecting the whole system.

d) Control Value (CV): Each line has a certain number of neighbours, n.

Each line, therefore, "gives" to each of its immediate neighbours $1/n$, and these numbers are then summed up for each receiving line, to give the CV of that space. This value is a measure of local relations, since it takes into account the relations of a line to its immediate neighbours. A line of high CV (above 1), may be considered to "control" many other lines, and that a person moving on it would be aware of things happening on a large number of neighbouring lines.

e) Global Value or Intelligibility (GV or I) is a number given to each line by dividing its CV by its RA. This number reflects the degree to which global integration is accompanied by strong control. In cases where GV is high, space becomes more intelligible, that is, it is relatively easy to be close and integrated with the whole system (thus being able to perceive something about the global properties of space) by standing on a line of strong control. Strong intelligibility may account for the legibility of space, that is the degree to which space allows people to orient themselves in it, with respect to the larger spatial structure.

f) Choice (CH): this measure shows how much of the total route choice in the whole system each space represents (how likely it is to be passed through) on all shortest routes from all spaces to all other spaces in the system (Hillier et al., 1986a). It is the predictor of movement for inhabitants. It is calculated by taking all the axially simplest routes from all spaces to all other spaces and then computing the proportion of the total movement in the system which passes through any space. Instead of integration, global choice is a dynamic aspect dealing with the route properties. The purpose of this measure is to detect the effects that certain spatial configurations have on the movement of people.

g) Movement Interface (MI) reveals places where interaction between strangers and inhabitants happens, that is places with high both

integration and choice values.

In the pre-1917 Plans of the city the spatial structure is analyzed in three scales:

- a) the city within-the-walls as a whole spatial system
- b) the "ethnoquarters" (4), the whole area one ethnicity occupies
- c) the city-neighbourhoods (28), areas occupied only by one ethnicity.

The 1917 Plan is analyzed in

- a) the city as a whole spatial system
- b) the planning units (28)

The mid-1970s and late 1980s Plans are analyzed in the scale of the city as a whole.

The spatial structure can be grossly divided in the public and private realm; the former includes

- a) the carrier (the city's outside world)
- b) the city's core
- c) central-area functions
- d) public open spaces
- e) public buildings (d and e subcategories of c)
- f) residential areas considered as units

The private realm consists of the whole range of private buildings and open spaces related to private landownership.

The study deals only with the public realm, since it is this that is dialectically related to its corresponding social super-structure.

As a carrier it is considered the broader public realm realising interaction between different spatial structures (i.e. cities).

The public buildings are considered separately for their importance in the maintenance and enhancement of the communities' social structure and identity.

"Ano-Polis" has kept up to now many of the initial attributes of its "organic" plan and this constitutes a reason to be analyzed as a part of the city's spatial structure, as well as in its own terms.

The axial map of each period is derived from the corresponding settlements' plan by drawing the least possible number of straight lines passing through its public open space. The lines are numbered and a matrix is constructed for each map showing for each line its connections with the other lines in the system. On the basis of this data, computer aided calculations are carried out, which give as an outcome the values referred above.

The non-distributed system of streets is not taken into account.

An overall review of the plans' spatial properties helps to compare quantitatively their different spatial structures by comparing the numerical values of each property for the whole range of systems. It also helps to and clarify their typologies. Finally, the qualitative analysis of each plan helps to extract the tools for comparisons between these typologies.

**CHAPTER III: THE CITY'S POLITICAL/ECONOMIC/SOCIAL
STRUCTURE**

3.1 The late Ottoman period

3.2. The City in 1920

**3.3. The City in the mid 1970s
and late 1980s**

3.1. The late Ottoman period

Thessalonika was the most significant centre of the Balkan peninsula that organised, specified and promoted the production and accumulation of the broader area; it developed as a market-co-ordinator of the rural production, a manufacture centre and mainly a centre of the international commerce (maps 1,2). It was one of the major nodes of the European invasion, therefore, it grew rapidly and doubled its population between 1860 and 1910 (60.000 to 120.000, map 3).

Up to 1917, the city's population was composed mainly of Turks, Jews and Greeks. The first Jews settled very early in the city (~200 B.C.) attracted by its excellent prospects for trade, while the Greeks had been the indigenous population.

Before the 15th century, since Jews were a minority in the city, they were hellenised, adopting the Greek language and social habits. The second major wave of Jewish immigrants that flooded the city driven out of all over Europe because of the increasing anti-semitic feelings in Germany, Portugal, Hungary, Italy and especially Spain, influenced the Greek-speaking Jews who gradually adopted the language of the Spanish ones and returned to the orthodox hebrew religion and social habits. This new homogeneous Jewish population remained as a distinct ethnic group throughout the five centuries of the Turkish occupation.

The Turks, that settled in the city after its fall in 1430, grew rapidly because of their government's privileges for the settlers in the new areas of the Empire, providing them with lands and houses previously belonging to Greeks. The city's infrastructure in streets and military installations facilitated this influx.

All along the period between 1430 and 1923 the three groups co-existed

-not always peacefully- and in spite of fluctuations of their numbers, they kept their separate religions, strong ethnic identities, forms of self-government, means of social reproduction and different roles in the city's functions.

The Turks were the dominant class and this set them apart from the Jews and the Greeks that were the oppressed citizens.

The highest authority figure of the city was the Turkish Pasha, supported by a military oligarchy and high officials responsible for giving justice and imposing and collecting taxes from the Greek and Jewish population. Nevertheless, a form of self-government had been allowed for the Greeks and the Jews. The last had been organised in a form of community council, its members being simultaneously their religious priests (rabbis in their 33 synagogues) with their own funds, used for religious, educational and communal purposes.

The community leaders of the Greeks were elected either through the influence of the church, or through secular circles. Their byzantine "council of twelve" consisted of priests and leaders of various guilds and was tied to the bishop's influence. The council elected a member to represent the minority to the Turkish government and looked after the distribution and collection of taxes from the community.

Religion was one of the main elements organising frequent interaction among people of the three distinct ethnicities. This is proved by the various religious buildings erected in the city (50 mosques, 33 synagogues, 15 christian churches). Apart from being centres of the religious activity, they also at times served as educational and cultural institutions, thus providing the means for the social reproduction of each group. Especially for the Greeks, the churches served all along half the millennium of the Turkish occupation as evening schools teaching the

Greek language, history and the Christian religious doctrine. Besides, in the late years of the Empire, the churches were the meeting places for the community's leaders. Thus, the links with the church, apart from clear religious purposes, contributed decisively to the preservation of the group's ethnical identity.

Concerning the educational and intellectual activities, the three groups had different purposes and means: the Turks gathered in "tekes", muslim monasteries where they studied and discussed religious issues, while the Jewish community, especially in the 19th century had been very active, spending large amounts of money for the education of their population.

The three groups participated in the life of the city through some distinct roles: the Turks were the rulers, government officials, military officers or idle landowners; they can't be included in the productive force of the city, for they mostly were living on the taxes collected from the Jews and the Greeks, as well as on the extremely high interest rates of the loans they lent to the merchants. They spent most of their time in public baths, "tekes" and cafes.

The Jews and Greeks were competing against each other, for the domination of the market.

The Greeks had some significant success in the long-distance, transcontinental trade, competing the Jews. However, their economic strength lay mostly in their numerous guilds of artisans and home manufacturers . Some Greeks as well as Jews had been employed as low-grade office employees in the Turkish government.

The Jews had expanded more their economic activity, being more successful in large-distance trading and contracting with merchants in the European cities. Nevertheless, the majority of the Jews were occupied in the local market, light home industry and few of them in the service

sector.

Up to the beginning of the 20th century, the city's population was organised socially and functionally primarily along ethnic divisions. The ethnic groups had their own forms of relative self-government, even though there was a central higher authority, their own religious, cultural and educational activities and institutions. Moreover, they held different functional responsibilities in the city's overall life. There was also a functional differentiation and specialisation within each group. The life of the three ethnic groups and of the city as a whole relied upon sharing a wide range of services and resources. Furthermore, the whole population contributed to and benefited from this interaction and interdependence.

This could possibly relate to Durkheim's ideas of organic and mechanical solidarities, where the strongly bound ethnic groups could be considered to form strong mechanical solidarities while all three ethnicities with their functional interdependence to form a weak organic solidarity. The city's social structure worked mainly on the correspondence model.

3.2. The city in 1920

In 1917 Thessalonika was the centre of Northern Greece with a diminished region around it, since the Balkan peninsula was distributed among many countries.

In the interwar period, the crisis in the economy, the increasing rural-urban contradiction and the commencement of an industrial dependence from centres of decisions out of the Greek boundaries influenced decisively the city's socioeconomic structure.

The impact of the first refugees from Asia Minor on the socio-economic structure is remarkable since they became the city's cheap labour force.

The population of 150.000 inhabitants found in 1913 has been increased significantly by refugees that found recourse in the city and protection by the forces of Alliance.

After the Balkan wars the city is at a flourishing stage due to the concourse of currency and the remarkable development of the market and services. This growth had an influence on the city's physical development as well.

The Greek immigrants from the country-side and the first refugees from Asia Minor contributed to the city's ethnical homogenisation. In 1920 there are 170.000 inhabitants with a proportion of 47% of Greek population and in 1928 there are 240.000 inhabitants with 83% Greeks, the rest 17% being mainly Jews.

Besides, the new social powers contribute decisively to a general reformulation of the city's social structure that starts working on the correspondence model not any more on ethnicity lines but on social-class differentiation. Now they are the poor that are differentiated (socially and as we could expect spatially) from the ascending middle class.

3.3. The city in the mid 1970s and late 1980s

In 1923 Greece and Turkey agreed to exchange the 1.075.000 Greeks of Asia Minor with the Turks still living in northern Greece. Thessalonika's Turkish population left the city and a much larger wave of Greek refugees inhabited it instantly. Before the population exchange the city was